

Supplementary Information
Recalibrating disease parameters for increasing realism in modeling
epidemics in closed settings

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Figure S1: Correlation between relative differences Δ .

Figure S2: Dependence of relative variations Δ on epidemic parameters.

Table S1: Correlations between relative variations Δ and reproductive number R_0^c .

Location (Full)	Δ_T vs. R_0^c		Δ_P vs. R_0^c		$\Delta_{\log \alpha}$ vs. R_0^c	
	r [95%CI]	p -value	r [95%CI]	p -value	r [95%CI]	p -value
Workplace	-0.6[-0.9, 0.2]	0.1	0.4[-0.3, 0.9]	0.2	-0.8[-1.0, -0.2]	0.01
School	-0.7[-0.9, -0.2]	0.02	0.6[-0.2, 0.9]	0.1	-0.9[-1.0, -0.6]	$< 10^{-3}$
Conference	-0.07[-0.70, 0.62]	0.85	1.0[0.9, 1.0]	$< 10^{-3}$	-0.9[-1.0, -0.7]	$< 10^{-3}$

Table S2: Correlations between relative variations Δ and recovery rate μ_c .

Location (Full)	Δ_T vs. μ_c		Δ_P vs. μ_c		$\Delta_{\log \alpha}$ vs. μ_c	
	r [95%CI]	p -value	r [95%CI]	p -value	r [95%CI]	p -value
Workplace	-0.2[-0.8, 0.5]	0.6	-0.3[-0.8, 0.4]	0.4	-0.1[-0.7, 0.6]	0.8
School	-0.2[-0.8, 0.5]	0.6	0.5[-0.2, 0.9]	0.2	0.3[-0.4, 0.8]	0.4
Conference	-0.3[-0.8, 0.4]	0.4	-0.3[-0.8, 0.5]	0.5	0.2[-0.6, 0.8]	0.6